

Beamforming and Functional Split Selection for Scalable Cell-free mMIMO Networks

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Abstract—The cell-free massive multiple-input multiple-output (CF mMIMO) spectral efficiency (SE) enhancement achieved through beamforming puts new requirements on the fronthaul interface load. At the same time, O-RAN is gaining traction thanks to standardized interfaces allowing for seamless integration of radio access network (RAN) components from different vendors. We propose fronthaul load estimation formulas for CF mMIMO with 7-1 and O-RAN-defined 7-2 functional splits that differ in the location of the beamforming function, which is essential in the CF mMIMO networks. Additionally, we propose a methodology of dynamic beamforming and functional split selection to minimize the fronthaul load while maintaining high sum SE utilization.

Index Terms—Cell-free massive MIMO, beamforming, functional split, fronthaul load, spectral efficiency, radio resource allocation algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION

CF mMIMO is an emerging mobile communication approach that departs from the traditional cellular network architecture. In cell-free mMIMO (CF mMIMO), instead of having a few centralized base stations (BSs) serving many users, the network is equipped with a large number of distributed access points (APs). These APs are densely deployed in a certain geographical area to provide unprecedented level of spectral efficiency (SE) performance of CF mMIMO networks [1], [2], [3]. In CF mMIMO, a multitude of APs are distributed across the coverage area and each user is served by multiple APs simultaneously. As is known, the sum SE of CF mMIMO depends on several factors, i.e., beamforming type, the noise level from adjacent APs, and the number of served users. The fronthaul load is increasing because multiple APs are involved in transmitting the data to the users. To provide a scalable CF mMIMO solution, the fronthaul load needs to be optimized for the current network state.

In this letter, we particularly follow the terminology from O-RAN specifications [4] where the precoding is applied to user equipment (UE) symbols of different layers (i.e., the independent data streams), and the beamforming is applied to the layer symbol transmitted from multiple antennas. The beamforming adaptation can significantly improve the sum SE of CF mMIMO [5]. The selection of the beamforming type and the functional split can reduce the fronthaul load which is

studied in this letter. Several research works are carried out to formulate the fronthaul load calculation of 3GPP split options in 5G and beyond radio access networks [6], [7], and [8].

The authors in [6] propose the formulas for fronthaul load calculation for several splits, including split 7.1 and 7.2. Moreover, dynamic split selection and resource allocation problems are formulated as a time-averaged stochastic optimization problem to evaluate the power saving of the elastic optical fronthaul architecture for 5G and beyond networks. The authors use the 7.2 split as defined in the 3GPP technical recommendation where the resource mapping building block is functionally executed below the split [11] at the radio unit, while in the O-RAN specifications for the 7-2x split [4], the resource mapping is performed at the distributed unit. To provide the trade-off between the cost and performance of selecting functional split, the authors in [7] provide a simplistic and unified model to directly compare the performance maximization and cost minimization of fully centralized and partially centralized 5G networks. Moreover, comprehensive simulation results are provided to estimate the cost and performance based on considering higher layer splits (e.g., PDCP-RLC, RLC-MAC, and MAC-PHY) of the radio protocol stacks in a different centralization level. Similarly, in [8] the authors analyze performance and operating costs aimed at the instantaneous network revenue maximization and provide a framework for the dynamic split decision. The proposed framework uses as inputs the operating cost in the current split, the operating cost in an optimal split, and the split change cost, however, the determination of the costs remains an open problem.

The future dense CF mMIMO networks may use wireless fronthaul [9]. In the case when RUs connected to an DU share common radio resources the sum fronthaul load becomes a limited resource. Therefore we investigate the fronthaul load dependence on the functional split and beamforming type. In summary, our contributions are highlighted as follows:

- We extend the 3GPP fronthaul load formulas of 7.1 and 7.2 functional split to the case of the CF mMIMO architecture assuming that the 7.2 3GPP and 7-2x O-RAN functional splits do not differ concerning the fronthaul

load. From now on, we will use the notation of the splits as 7-1 and 7-2.

- We use the proposed formulas to calculate the 7-2 and 7-1 fronthaul load for the CF mMIMO resource allocation in [10], which aims at the sum SE maximisation.
- Because the fronthaul load increases with the number of serving RUs, but also the sum SE increases, therefore, we propose a methodology for obtaining a trade-off between sum fronthaul load minimisation and sum SE maximisation. The proposed methodology dynamically selects the beamforming type and functional split.

The rest of the letter is organized as follows. In section II, we discuss the system model and formulate the problem of dynamic beamforming adaptation and functional split selection. In section III, we propose the fronthaul load formulas for CF mMIMO system and describe the radio resource allocation algorithms. In section IV, we present and discuss the simulation results. In section V, we conclude our paper also indicating future research directions.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. System model

Let us consider a CF mMIMO system with M antennas that may coherently transmit in the same resource element¹ to U user equipments (UEs). The system consists of B subcarriers, where 12 consecutive subcarriers in the frequency domain compose a physical resource block (PRB) [13]. The PRBs are allocated to UEs by the radio resource allocation algorithm, which may also decide to send L layers, i.e., independent data, to a UE in a PRB. Let s_{ulb} be modulated and preceded complex symbol to be transmitted to UE u on layer l in a subcarrier b . Before the transmission, the beamforming function located either in the Radio Unit (RU) or in the Distributed Unit (DU), as shown in Fig. 1, linearly beamforms the UE layer symbols s_{ulb} to antenna symbols x_{mb} (for notation see Table I):

$$x_{mb} = \sum_u^U \sum_l^L w_{mub} s_{ulb}, \quad (1)$$

where w_{mub} denotes a complex beamforming factor applied for symbol s_{ulb} transmission from the antenna m and $|w_{mub}|^2$ is the allocated downlink transmit power at antenna m for the layer l of UE u in subcarrier b . Section II-B explains the impact of the beamforming function placement in the network.

We further assume single-antenna UEs for which the network transmits one layer without precoding, thus, for simplicity, we drop the layer index l :

$$x_{mb} = \sum_u^U w_{mub} s_{ub}, \quad (2)$$

¹The resource element is the smallest orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) time-frequency resource of an OFDM symbol duration and a subcarrier frequency width.

TABLE I
NOTATION

Symbols	Meaning
M	Number of antennas
Index m	Antenna index
U	Number of UEs
Index u	UE index
L	Number of independent layers of UE
Index l	Layer index
B	Number of subcarriers in the carrier bandwidth
Index b	Subcarrier index
s	Transmitted symbol
y	Received signal
h	Channel
w	Beamforming factor
SINR	Signal-to-interference and noise ratio
n	Noise
SE	Spectral efficiency (bit/Hz)
κ	Sum SE utilization
W	Carrier bandwidth (MHz)
F	Beamforming type, MRT or ZF
Γ	Basic fronthaul load (Mbit/s)
q	IQ bitwidth (bit)
R	Fronthaul load (Mbit/s)
7-1, 7-2	functional split type 7-1 or 7-2
γ	Fronthaul signalling overhead: $\gamma_{7-2} = 713.9$ Mbit/s, $\gamma_{7-1} = 121$ Mbit/s
r	RU index
K	Number of RU antennas
ν	User bandwidth utilisation
μ	Antenna bandwidth utilisation
\hat{M}	Number of serving antennas
\hat{F}	Selected beamforming type
P_{\max}	Maximum antenna transmit power per subcarrier

and the single layer received signal y_{ub} at UE u in the subcarrier b can be written as:

$$y_{ub} = \sum_m^M \sum_{u'}^U h_{umb} w_{mu'b} s_{u'b} + n_{ub}, \quad (3)$$

where h_{umb} is the complex-valued channel coefficient between the receiving UE u and transmit antenna m in subcarrier b , the u' denotes the UE for which the signal is transmitted, thus, the UE u will receive through the channel h_{umb} symbols $s_{u'b}$ transmitted to all UEs and the beamforming $w_{mu'b}$ can be used to suppress the interference caused by UE u' . The n_{ub} is the noise at UE u in a subcarrier b . The noise is the sum of the thermal noise and the ambient external (i.e., inter-system) interference.

The UE received signal-to-interference and noise (SINR) in subcarrier b is the total received power divided by the total interference power in the subcarrier, where interference

Fig. 1. The functional split options: (a) O-RAN-defined 7-2 split with beamforming at the RU [4], (b) 7-1 split with beamforming at the DU.

is caused by transmission to other users u' :

$$\text{SINR}_{ub} = \frac{\left| \sum_m^M h_{umb} w_{mub} \right|^2}{\sum_{u' \neq u}^U \left| \sum_m^M h_{um'b} w_{mu'b} \right|^2 + E\left\{ |n_{ub}|^2 \right\}}. \quad (4)$$

The system achievable downlink spectral efficiency, referred to as the *sum SE*, denoted by SE_{DL} , can be expressed as:

$$\text{SE}_{\text{DL}} = \frac{1}{B} \sum_b^B \sum_u^U \log_2(1 + \text{SINR}_{ub}). \quad (5)$$

B. Fronthaul load definition

The key aspect of the CF mMIMO system is the beamforming, which allows for transmission of the same symbol s_{ubl} from several antennas with different beamforming factors, i.e., amplitude and phase shift. In the literature, this operation is also referred to as the precoding, but to follow the O-RAN terminology illustrated in Fig. 1, we use the term of precoding for coding different layers (i.e., different symbols) and the term of beamforming for applying phase shift to the same layer (i.e., the same symbol) transmitted from multiple antennas. We consider two beamforming types, F : the maximum ratio transmission (MRT) aiming at maximization of the received signal amplitude, and the zero forcing (ZF) aiming at minimization of the interference caused to other receivers. In the functional split 7-2, shown in Fig. 1a, the beamforming function is located at the RU and in the functional split 7-1, shown in Fig. 1b, the beamforming function is located at the DU. The two splits are the most interesting from the CF mMIMO fronthaul load consideration

Let R_{7-2} be the 7-2 split sum fronthaul load, i.e., the number of bits transmitted per second from the DU to all RUs in

functional split 7-2. The R_{7-2} includes the transmission of the complex values s_{ubl} as well as the additional overhead of signaling between DU and RU related to split 7-2.

Let R_{7-1} be the 7-1 split fronthaul load, i.e., the number of bits transmitted per second from DU to all RUs in functional split 7-1. The R_{7-1} is the 7-1 split fronthaul load, which includes the transmission of the complex values x_{nb} as well as the additional overhead of signaling between the DU and RU related to split 7-1.

C. Problem formulation

To maintain the sum SE high and the sum fronthaul load low, while both of them increase with the number of serving antennas, we propose to sacrifice a small percentage of the maximum achievable sum SE, e.g., 2%, and determine the minimum number of serving antennas, \hat{M} , to achieve the sum SE utilization of at least $\kappa = 98\%$. For the determined \hat{M} and resulting beamforming type, \hat{F} , we choose the functional split, 7-2 or 7-1, which provides the lower fronthaul load. The process, performed dynamically for the actual number of served UEs and the number of RU antennas, can be expressed as follows:

$$\min_{\text{functional split}} R(\text{functional split}, \hat{F}, \hat{M}), \quad (6)$$

subjected to:

$$\text{SE}_{\text{DL}}(\hat{F}, \hat{M}) \geq \kappa \max_{F, M} \text{SE}_{\text{DL}}(F, M) \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_u^U |w_{mub}|^2 \leq P_{\max}, \quad (8)$$

where P_{\max} is the maximum transmit power of an antenna per subcarrier and κ is the sum SE utilization, which is the scheduling algorithm constrain. The scheduling algorithm should output the minimized number of serving antennas required to provide at least a fraction of κ of the maximum sum SE possible to achieve without the κ constrain, as expressed in (7). \hat{F} is the beamforming type which applied to the selected \hat{M} antennas yields the sum SE utilization of κ .

III. CF mMIMO FRONTHAUL LOAD

We aim at estimating the 7-2 and 7-1 split sum fronthaul load for the CF mMIMO system. First, based on [12], [11], we define the *basic fronthaul load*, Γ , resulting from sending one IQ-value per resource element:

$$\Gamma = N_s \times T_s \times N_{\text{cs}} \frac{W}{20} \times q \quad (\text{Mbit/s}), \quad (9)$$

where $N_s = 14$ is the number of OFDM symbols in a slot, $T_s = 0.001$ s is the slot duration for subcarrier spacing of 15 kHz, $N_{\text{sc}} = 1200$ is the number of subcarriers in a 20 MHz bandwidth carrier, W is the actual carrier bandwidth in MHz and q is the IQ-value bitwidth. The formula developed for 15 kHz subcarrier spacing and 20 MHz carrier bandwidth

[12] applies to any subcarrier spacing and carrier bandwidth [11]. For $W = 20$ MHz bandwidth and bitwidth $q = 32$ bits, $\Gamma = 537.6$ Mbit/s.

A. 7-2 split fronthaul load

In CF mMIMO with the 7-2 functional split, the UE signal, s_{ulb} , is sent over fronthaul to all RUs involved in the radio transmission to the UE. The RU fronthaul load scales with the number of UEs served by the RU, and the number of layers, L , thus, we propose the following 7-2 functional split sum fronthaul load estimation:

$$R_{7-2} = \sum_r \left(\Gamma \sum_{u \in r} L \nu_u + \gamma_{7-2} \right), \quad (10)$$

where the inner summation concerns UEs u served by the RU r , the $\gamma_{7-2} = 713.9$ Mbps is the fronthaul signalling overhead for 7-2 split [11] and ν_u is the bandwidth utilisation of UE u modelled as:

$$\nu_u = \frac{1}{B} \sum_b \dot{s}_{ulb}, \quad (11)$$

where the dot symbol denotes the usage of a resource:

$$\dot{s}_{ulb} = \begin{cases} 0, & s_{ulb} = 0 \\ 1, & s_{ulb} \neq 0. \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Introduction of the UE bandwidth utilization, ν_u , implies that symbols s_{ulb} on unused subcarriers are not transferred over fronthaul, but the RE Mapping function of the DU indicates to the RU their disuse. The UE bandwidth utilization depends on the radio resource allocation algorithm (see section III-C).

B. 7-1 split fronthaul load

In the CF mMIMO with the 7-1 functional split, the beamformed data, x_{nb} , per antenna is sent over fronthaul. The RU fronthaul load scales with the number of serving antennas, i.e., antennas that are involved in a transmission to any UE, thus, we propose the following 7-1 functional split sum fronthaul load formula:

$$R_{7-1} = \sum_r \left(\Gamma \sum_{n \in r} \mu_n + \gamma_{7-1} \right), \quad (13)$$

where μ_n is the bandwidth utilization of the antenna n and $\gamma_{7-1} = 121$ Mbps is the fronthaul signalling overhead for 7-1 split [11]. Considering that an IQ-value x_{nb} in (2) and Fig. 1b is only sent if the (n, b) resource is used, the antenna bandwidth utilization is modeled as:

$$\mu_n = \frac{1}{B} \sum_b \dot{x}_{nb}, \quad (14)$$

where the dot symbol defined in (12) denotes the usage of the x_{nb} resource. The antenna bandwidth utilization, μ_n , depends on the CF mMIMO resource allocation algorithm.

C. CF mMIMO radio resource allocation

The ν_u in (10) and μ_n in (13) depend on the radio resource allocation algorithm. We use the algorithms in [10] which determine the serving antennas for each UE to maximize the sum SE:

- Heuristic radio resource scheduling algorithm for MRT beamforming, MRT-H2, and
- Heuristic radio resource scheduling algorithm for ZF beamforming, ZF-H.

The algorithms provide an optimized sequence in which antennas should be considered for serving. An antenna considered for serving is selected for serving if it yields improved sum SE. Thus, the algorithms can provide the sum SE as a function of the number of best antennas considered for serving.

The MRT beamforming factors are independent between UEs and can be determined locally at the RU simplifying the implementation while the ZF beamforming factors need to be determined centrally at the DU.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The simulated network of size $320 \text{ m} \times 277 \text{ m}$ contains $M = 64$ distributed omnidirectional antennas with 2.15 dBi gain located 10 m above the ground, as listed in Table II. Each antenna can transmit 4 GHz carrier of $W = 18$ MHz bandwidth consisting of 600 subcarriers with 30 kHz spacing and maximum power $P_{\max} = 0.833$ mW per subcarrier. Fig. 2 shows the system topology with $K = 4$ antennas per RU, $K \in \{1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64\}$. In 100 simulation iterations $U \in \{5, 10, 20\}$ stationary single antenna UEs with infinite data buffer have been randomly distributed in the network and the channel has been modeled according to [15] and [14]. Three noise power levels of -90 dBm, -70 dBm, and -50 dBm per PRB, have been simulated. For each noise power level and the number of UEs, U , the mean sum SE as a function of the number of best antennas considered for serving has been computed using MRT and ZF radio resource allocation algorithms. After the serving antennas have been determined according to (7), the fronthaul load, R , has been estimated for each K .

Fig. 3 shows the sum SE performance of the heuristic radio resource allocation algorithms as a function of the number of best antennas considered for serving 10 UEs. This dependence demonstrates an asymptotic sum SE growth and the color dots indicate the number of best antennas considered for serving when the sum SE yields $\kappa = 0.98$ of its utilization. E.g., for ZF at noise -90 dBm, 32 antennas are enough to serve 10 UEs, and for MRT, 23 antennas. In the case of ZF, additional antennas would increase the sum SE by less than 2% and, in the case of MRT, they could even increase interference more than the signal. The proposed beamforming adaptation algorithm selects the beamforming type yielding a higher sum SE for 98% utilization, e.g., for 10 UEs and -90 dBm noise, the ZF yields a higher sum SE of 127 bit/s/Hz compared to 71 bit/s/Hz

TABLE II
SYSTEM CHARACTERISTIC

Characteristic	Value
Environment	Dense urban micro
No. of antennas, M	64
No. of antennas per RU, K	{1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64}
Inter-antenna distance	40 m
Serving area	320 m \times 277 m
Antenna height	10 m
Antenna gain	2.15 dBi
Carrier frequency	4 GHz
Subcarrier spacing	30 kHz
Bandwidth, W	18 MHz (50 PRBs)
P_{\max}	0.833 mW (10 dBm per PRB)
Noise power per PRB	{-90 dBm, -70 dBm, -50 dBm}
Number of UEs, U	{5, 10, 20}
Traffic model	Full buffer
Time	1 TTI
Mobility	Stationary
Channel knowledge	Full
Spectral efficiency	Shannon capacity

Fig. 2. Simulated network topology with sixteen 4-antenna RUs marked with red circles and random location of UEs marked with green dots.

for MRT, therefore the ZF beamforming is selected, as shown in the summary Fig. 5. At noise of -50 dBm, the MRT yields a higher sum SE than the ZF, as the ZF is not able to provide a strong enough signal to overcome the high noise.

Fig 4 shows the fronthaul load dependence on the number of RU antennas for different noise power and the $\kappa = 0.98$. At the noise of -90 dBm and ZF, when 10 UEs are served with 32 antennas, 1-antenna RUs yield only 25 Gbit/s fronthaul load with 7-1 split and 218 Gbit/s with 7-2 split, where 10 times more use data symbols are sent because of 10 UEs served by each antenna. The split yielding lower fronthaul load for the already selected beamforming type, in this case 7-1, is indicated in the summary Fig. 5. It can also be seen in Fig 4, that the 7-2 split fronthaul load strongly decreases when the number

Fig. 3. Mean sum SE dependence on the number of antennas considered for serving 10 UEs in 64-antenna CF mMIMO system.

Fig. 4. Fronthaul load for 64-antenna CF mMIMO system serving 10 UEs with sum SE utilization of $\kappa = 0.98$.

of RU antennas grows, which is due to two reasons. The first reason, which is dominant in the case of the ZF where an antenna serves all 10 UEs, is fewer user data symbols sent on fronthaul due to fewer RUs. The second reason, which is dominant in the MRT where an antenna serves one UE, is lower fronthaul overhead also due to fewer RUs. Another observation, clearly visible for 64-antenna RU, where the overhead load is negligible, is the 7-2 fronthaul load dependence on the number of UEs, which is 10, and the 7-2 split dependence on the number of antennas, which, depending on the beamforming type and noise level, is 22 or more.

Fig. 5 illustrates the beamforming and functional split selection algorithm, where it can be seen, that:

- As expected, in low ambient noise of -90 dBm, the ZF, which does not introduce additional interference, yields a higher sum SE, but in high noise of -50 dBm, the MRT,

Beamforming type	ZF 238	Mean sum SE [bit/s/Hz]
Functional split	7-1 33.6	Fronthaul load [Gbit/s]

Number of UEs	Noise = -90 dBm			Noise = -70 dBm			Noise = -50 dBm		
	Beamforming type	Functional split	Mean sum SE [bit/s/Hz]	Beamforming type	Functional split	Mean sum SE [bit/s/Hz]	Beamforming type	Functional split	Mean sum SE [bit/s/Hz]
20	ZF	238	238	ZF	109	109	MRT	33	33
10	ZF	127	127	ZF	62	62	MRT	22	22
5	ZF	67	67	MRT	37	37	MRT	14	14

Fig. 5. Dependence of the beamforming type and functional split on the number of UEs, the noise power, and the number of RU antennas.

which increases the received signal power, is superior to the ZF. In a medium noise of -70 dBm ZF performs better for 10 and 20 UEs, but MRT for 5 UEs.

- In all configurations in Fig. 5, the ZF yields a lower fronthaul load with the 7-1 split than with the 7-2 split, but, for RUs with more antennas, 7-2 split starts to be advantageous compared to the 7-1 split, e.g., at noise of -70 dBm, 7-2 split yields lower fronthaul load than 7-1 split with 16 or more antenna RUs, as seen in Fig 4.
- The MRT yields a lower fronthaul load with the 7-1 split when RU is equipped with one or two antennas. For 4 or more antennas at the RU, the 7-2 split yields a lower fronthaul load.
- For 1 and 2-antenna RUs, it is enough for the network to support the 7-1 split. For RUs equipped with more than 16 antennas, it is enough for the network to support the 7-2 split. For RUs equipped with more than 2 but up to 16 antennas, the network should support both 7-1 and 7-2 split to dynamically adjust the split depending on the number of UEs and noise power.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We extend the 7-2 and 7-1 functional splits fronthaul load formulas proposed by 3GPP to support the CF mMIMO network architectures. According to the formulas, the fronthaul load depends on the radio resource allocation algorithm. To illustrate the fronthaul load we use the radio resource allocation algorithms that maximize the sum SE to find the beamforming type, MRT or ZF, yielding a higher sum SE at its 98% utilization, and the number of serving antennas. Next, for the chosen beamforming type and a dynamic network state defined by the number of UEs and the noise power, we choose the functional split yielding lower fronthaul load. We show, that for RUs equipped with from 4 to 16 antennas, either 7-1 or 7-2 functional split yield a lower fronthaul load depending on the dynamic network state, therefore the dynamic functional split selection can lower the CF mMIMO sum fronthaul load. Future works could take into account the uplink fronthaul load and maximize energy efficiency of cell-free mMIMO networks.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

6G-BRICKS project has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grand Agreement No 101096954.

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